

EFFECTIVENESS OF BARICITINIB IN THE BASIC THERAPY OF ACTIVE RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS

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The purpose of our study was to evaluate the efficacy and safety of baricitinib (BARI) in patients with rheumatoid arthritis (RA) who have not achieved low activity or remission according to EULAR criteria under the influence of synthetic disease-modifying drugs or biological agents.

Materials and methods. 10 patients with a definite diagnosis of RA were under observation (ACR-1987, EULAR-2010 criteria). Among the included patients, there were 7 women and three men, ranging in age from 31 to 64 years (mean age 51.67 years). The patients had an advanced (in 3 patients) or late (in 7 patients) clinical stage of erosive arthritis with predominant damage to the small joints of the hands, the radiological stage was not lower than 3. Seropositive variant of RA was diagnosed in 9 patients, seronegative rheumatoid factor (RF) variant of RA occurred in 1 patient. All patients were seropositive for ADC antibodies to cyclic citrullinated peptide. The degree of disease activity according to the DAS28 index ranged from 4.71 to 6.65 points (average value 5.81 ± 2.1 points), and in 13 patients it corresponded to the level of high activity (DAS28 index > 5.1) and only in 2 people the DAS28 index was less than 5.1 points.

All patients received standard antirheumatic therapy before the appointment of BARI, which was not effective enough. Due to the continued activity of the disease, all patients were prescribed BARI at a dose of 4 mg once a day (a daily dose of 4 mg).

The analysis was carried out taking into account BARI therapy for 6 months: monthly monitoring of the effectiveness and safety of the treatment regimen used. The effectiveness of BARI therapy was assessed based on the dynamics of clinical and laboratory parameters reflecting the activity of RA: dynamics of the DAS28-4 index (ESR), CDAI, SDAI, RAPID3, ACR criteria 20/50/70. Along with this, we took into account the dynamics of generally accepted immunological parameters – C-reactive protein (CRP) and RF. Assessment of the safety of therapy with the inclusion of BARI was carried out by recording possible adverse events associated with taking the studied drug, as well as based on the dynamics of standard laboratory tests.

Clinical and laboratory parameters were monitored with an analysis of the initial parameters and their dynamics after 3 and 6 months.

The results of the study. As noted earlier, the baseline values, primarily the DAS28 index, in the vast majority of patients (86.67%) corresponded to the level of high disease activity. At the same time, it should be emphasized that after 1 month, under the influence of BARI treatment, positive dynamics was observed in a number of clinical and laboratory parameters: there was a decrease in the DAS28, CDAI, SDAI, RAPID indices, combined in a number of patients with a decrease in ESR, CRP and RF. After 3 months. After treatment with BARI, there was a further decrease in the clinical signs of RA activity, while there was a significant decrease in the DAS28 index compared to the baseline value in all 10 patients: from 1.09 to 2.50 points (by an average of 1.61 points). The positive dynamics of all the indices used was significant already at the stage of the 3-month course of therapy, with a decrease in the simplified activity indices (SDAI and CDAI) occurring by more than 50%. After 6 months of treatment, all total indicators of RA activity remained at the achieved level for 3 months and were also significantly lower than the corresponding indices at the time of inclusion in the study. Moreover, after 6 months of treatment, only one patient had high RA activity according to the DAS28 index, although this indicator decreased by 1 point compared to the baseline value.

As follows from the presented results, the average number of painful joints decreased from 11.6 to 5.4 after 3 months and to 4.6 after 6 months of treatment, and the average number of swollen joints decreased from 7.1 to 2 and 1.7, respectively. At the same time, all patients noted an improvement in their overall health after both 3 and 6 months of treatment, which was reflected in the average values of this indicator, which decreased by almost half. As for the laboratory parameters, their dynamics turned out to be less pronounced. Nevertheless, when analyzing the changes in CRP and RF using nonparametric statistics, we found significant differences compared to the initial indicators.

As for serious adverse events, they were not reported in any of the 10 patients, all controlled generally accepted laboratory parameters remained within normal values, with the exception of one patient who had a transient increase in aminotransferase levels by no more than 20% of the initial normal level. The patients' adherence to the treatment of BARI was satisfactory.

In conclusion, it should be noted that based on our clinical observations on the use of BARI in RA, we have obtained convincing evidence of the high efficacy

and safety of this drug in patients with insufficient response to standard basic RA therapy.

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